

Cao Đài

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Cao Đài is a syncretic indigenous Vietnamese religion that was born out of the milieu of the Mekong Delta region of Vietnam and the borderlands of Vietnam and Cambodia. Although the religion is monotheistic, it also intentionally blends elements of Catholicism, Vietnamese folk traditions, Chinese religions (especially the sanjiao or tâm giáo, Daoism, Confucianism, and Chinese influenced/Chinese Buddhism), and more global understandings of revelation. For instance, the Prophet Muhammed is considered part of the "Prophets of the Christian Era" along with the Prophet Baab (Bahai'i), Moses (Judaism), and Jesus (Christianity). The religion was founded by Ngô Văn Chiêu, who was a Vietnamese administrator and district head in the French colony of Cochinchina. Officially, this new religion became name as the Đại Đạo Tam Kỳ Phổ Độ (Great way of the Third Time of Redemption," indicating the perception that the early 20th century was to be a new era of revealed truth. Thus, it is not entirely surprising that modern historical figures, such as the French author Victor Hugo, the Chinese nationalist Sun Yat Sen, and Vietnamese national poet-saint, Nguyễn Bình Khiêm (1491-1585) were established as saints. During the First Indochina War, the Cao Đài movement formed their own militia, which was then subordinated to the Republic of Vietnam military (ARVN) during the Second Indochina War. Typically anti-communist during the Second Indochina War, Cao Đài militia members were treated with extra scrutiny during and after the subsequent reunification of Vietnam in 1976. Consequentially, substantial Cao Đài diasporas can be found in France, the United States, Canada and Australia. However, after normalization of relations between Vietnam and the United States in 1995, during a period of liberalization in the late 1990s, Cao Đài recognition in Vietnam was officially granted in 1997. Thus, after 1997, Cao Đài practice has been relatively unrestricted and formally recognized. In recent decades, splinter schools or offshoots of the officially recognized Cao Đài religion have complained about scolding and harassment from state sanctioned Cao Đài authorities. Such debates have emerged in a context where state-sanctioned religious sites, especially the main Cao Đài temple in Tây Ninh province--just north of Hồ Chí Minh City, have become major sites for the international tourist community to visit. Finally, in the past two decades, the role of remissions from the diaspora community to Cao Đài organizations in Vietnam has become increasingly significant.

Date Range: 1921 CE - 2024 CE

Region: Cao Đài Communities, Contemporary Vietnam & USA

Region tags: San Francisco, San Diego, Sacramento, Tây Ninh, TP. Hồ Chí Minh, TP. Cần Thơ, Vĩnh Long, Tiền Giang, United States, Vietnam, California, Garden Grove

This map represents the geographic distribution of the main sites of Cao Đài communities in contemporary Vietnam. The main community, the Tây Ninh Holy See, is just northwest of Hồ Chí Minh City. There are also concentrations sprinkled from Hồ Chí Minh City through the Mekong Delta, southwest toward Vĩnh Long and Cần Thơ. Significant diaspora communities also exist in Garden Grove, Orange

County, California (USA), along with Sacramento, San Francisco, and San Diego.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Kinh Thiên Đạo Và Thế Đạo (Prayers of the Heavenly and the Earthly Way)

– Source 2: Pháp Chánh Truyền (the Religious Constitution of Cao Đài Religion)

– Source 3: Tân Luật (The Canonical Codes)

– Source 1: Con Đường Thiêng Liêng Hằng Sống (Divine Path to Eternal Life)

Notes: While these four texts represent the main "texts" of the Cao Đài religious elite, there are additional texts that are used by individual temples or schools that are specific to those locations.

– Source 1: Jammes, Jeremy (2010). Divination and Politics in Southern Vietnam: Roots of Caodaism. *Social Compass* 57(3), 357-371

– Source 2: Blagov, Sergei (2012). *Caodaism: Vietnamese Traditionalism and Its Leap Into Modernity*. Nova Science Publishers.

– Source 3: Jammes, Jeremy (2014). *Les Oracles du Cao Dai: Étude d'un mouvement religieux vietnamien et de ses réseaux*. Paris: Les Indes Savantes.

Notes: These are secondary sources worth examining for this entry.

– Source 1: Hoskins, Janet Alison (2015). *The Divine Eye and the Diaspora: Vietnamese syncretism becomes transpacific Caodaism*. Honolulu: University of Hawaii Press.

– Source 2: Hoskins, Janet Alison (2012). *What Are Vietnam's Indigenous Religions? (Report)*. Center for Southeast Asian Studies, Kyoto University. pp. 4-6.

Notes: The work of anthropologist Janet Hoskins has been very important for shedding light on the Cao Đài religion.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://caodai.com.vn/en>

– Source 1 Description: This is the English portal for the official Cao Đài website in Vietnam.

– Source 2 URL: <https://caodai.com.vn/vn>

– Source 2 Description: This is the Vietnamese language portal for the official Cao Đài website in Vietnam.

– Source 3 URL: <https://caodai.com.vn/df>

– Source 3 Description: This is the French language portal for the official Cao Đài website in Vietnam.

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL: <https://thuvien.caodai.com.vn/en/index.html>

– Source 1 Description: Library Cao Đài is an online library that includes downloadable versions of Cao Đài

religious texts in .pdf format.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: Cao Đài leaders have competed for membership with other religious groups throughout modern Vietnamese history, especially Hòa Hảo Buddhism, both protestant and catholic Christianity, and with other "Vietnamese religions," being predominantly Buddhist groups and indigenous religious practices. The nature of this competition has been sporadically more significant in specific eras (such as the 1920s through the 1940s) although it has become less significant over time.

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: Cao Đài religion intentionally self-articulates as universalist, pan-theistic, pluralist, and accommodating. While there has been violent conflict between members of this religion and other religions historically, the nature of this conflict was not necessarily explicitly religious. Some recent efforts by Cao Đài leadership have been to articulate their religion in conversation with other intentionally syncretic religions, such as Bahai religion.

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

Notes: Much cultural contact with the surrounding Vietnamese religious community, as well as the religious communities of minority religions in the region (especially Cham Muslims) has been relatively neutral.

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: Especially during the First Indochina War (1945-1954) but also during the early days of the Second Indochina War (1955-1975), the Cao Đài militia group fought violently against members of other religions. Their militia, headed by General Trình Minh Thế, began as a Japanese supported paramilitary operation in the 1940s. However, Trình Minh Thế would split from the main Cao Đài militia in 1951, turning his forces against both the French troops and the Việt Minh (communist-nationalist independence movement). The group was responsible for several bombings and assassinations, while the rump guard of the traditionalist Cao Đài militia was concentrated on community defense. Then, Edward Lansdale, an American CIA agent, negotiated directly with Trình Minh Thế and secured an agreement for him to join the Army of the Republic of Vietnam at the rank of general in 1955, de facto ending the most violent days of

the Cao Đài militia as an independent force. Further, Trinh Minh Thế was assassinated on May 3, 1955, forcing the remainder of his troops to secure closer ties of loyalty among their networks in the ARVN forces, in hopes of avoiding a similar fate.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– Yes

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

Notes: Like many Vietnamese, Southeast Asian, and Asian religions, the Cao Đài religion is based on an understanding of praxis, in combination with doctrine. While doctrine plays a more significant role for Cao Đài members, the de facto nature of membership is predominantly through family-association with particular temples. Any community with more than 500 members may establish a "parish," and so there is some understanding that membership includes participation in the community, support of community ritual and financial support (if possible) of the Cao Đài organization.

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– Yes [specify]: Marriage into the community is an acceptable method of conversion.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– No

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– No

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– Yes

Notes: With the caveat that all Cao Đài work outside of Vietnam is considered to be the work of "foreign missions" using very similar language to how Catholic communities in Vietnam self-articulated during the French colonial era. At the same time, proselytization is not a strong focus of these communities.

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– No

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1955 CE - 1975 CE

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– No

Notes: Unless said priests were also members of the government or administration, or military, they were not paid directly. However, priests and other religious officiants did receive funds during the period of the Republic of Vietnam, which they used to support their community, even if the funds were not explicitly granted under those auspices.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1955 CE - 1975 CE

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– No

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– No

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– Yes

Notes: Or, rather, the reverse. Religious officials were especially equivalent to political officials in their roles in negotiating between their communities and French Indochina, the Republic of Vietnam, and the subsequent Socialist Republic of Vietnam.

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– No

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– No

Notes: However, at the village level in colonial-era Vietnam, the distinction between a religious code enforced by local officials and the legal code of a particular area may have been moot. We should not understand French or Vietnamese law as intentionally coterminous with religious law beyond the village/town level. Since reunification (1976), Vietnamese law and administrative code has been entirely separate from the authority of Cao Đài leadership, although the position of the community in Tây Ninh ensures some blurring in that location.

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)

– No

Notes: There is no historical evidence of tax exemption in Vietnam.

– Yes

Notes: There is evidence of Cao Đài organizations receiving tax exempt status in the United States after 1975. When tax exempt status began is not particularly clear and is likely specific to each temple and community organization in the United States.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1975 CE - 2024 CE

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Notes: As a result of the pantheistic and universalist qualities of Cao Đài religion, it is virtually impossible for joining another religious group to be considered apostasy in any sense of the term. Much more likely, existing believers and members would be interpreting such actions as a revelation of the particularities of the universal truth of the great divine eye, as all "Ways" and "paths" are considered equal.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 4000000

Notes: Estimates on the total population of Cao Đài adherents across the world vary substantially. The Cao Đài organization in the United States claims 6 million in the global organization, which seems too high. A 2009 survey in Vietnam, where most Cao Đài reside, found approximately 800k adherents, while a 2014 data-point from Cao Đài.net lists around 30k overseas between the populations of France, the United States, and Australia. With a small number of adherents elsewhere in the Europe and a small population in Cambodia and Canada, it seems that the diaspora population does not exceed 50k or so. At the same time, a reliable survey from Vietnam's government board of religious affairs (Ban Tôn giáo Chính phủ) found that there were 2.4-2.5 million adherents in 2010. Given average rates of population growth in the country, and across the globe, an accurate high-end estimate for global population of Cao Đài seems like it would sit closer to 4 million (rather than 6 million).

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 2.7

Notes: In all of Vietnam, Cao Đài represent 2.7% of the population. Within the sample communities where Cao Đài temples are indicated on the general maps for this entry, the percentage of the population is probably much higher (in Vietnam), while the percentage of the population is probably much lower (less than 1%) of the general population in selected sample regions of the main maps for this entry outside of Vietnam (i.e.: in California).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Vietnam

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– Yes

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– Yes

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– Yes

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– Yes

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Percentage: 10

Notes: Since settlements in Vietnam are not exclusive to religious group in the period in question, the Cao Đài religious architecture typically does not represent more than 10%, or less-sometimes much less-of the given area within the sample region.

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Square meters: 2145

Notes: The location of the main temple is: Tòa Thánh Tây Ninh, Đại lộ Phạm Hộ Pháp, phường Long Hoa, thị xã Hòa Thành, tỉnh Tây Ninh.

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 28.2

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Height, square meters: 1000

Notes: This is an estimate. Most temples are less than half the size of the main Cao Đài temple

in Tây Ninh.

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 10

Notes: The average height of Cao Đài temples is much smaller than the height of the main temple. Most are around one story, so at least 4-5m tall, but almost certainly under 10-15 m tall.

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Percentage of area: 2

Notes: The total area is around 1 square kilometer and only approximate 2,000 sq meters is taken up by the main temple. However, there are subordinate structures at the site, which are religious in nature, increasing the size of the site taken up by "religious monuments."

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– No

↳ Cemeteries:

– Yes

↳ Temples:

– Yes

Notes: The main Tây Ninh Holy See temple of the Cao Đài has numerous subordinate temples and shrines associated with it.

↳ Altars:

– Yes

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

- Yes [specify]: Subordinate shrines are an important part of temple sites in Vietnamese culture. They are quite common and it is possible to interpret subordinate structures at the main Cao Đài temple (Tòa Thánh Tây Ninh/ the Tây Ninh Holy See) as having subordinate shrine sites associated with it.

Is iconography present:

- Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

- On persons
- At home
- Only religious public space
- Some public spaces
- All public spaces

Notes: Iconography in the Cao Đài religion is virtually omnipresent. It is most notable for its syncretism of Christian, spiritualist, Vietnamese, Chinese, European, and Asian elements, all intentionally carrying the universalist message of Cao Đài.

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

- Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

- Yes

Notes: The most common stylized eye is the "Left Eye of Cao Đài" which resembles an all-seeing eye. See answer on "Supernatural beings (abstract symbol) for more details.

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

- Yes

Notes: Dragons, in particular, are very common supernatural zoomorphic beings that are represented.

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

- Yes

Notes: In the main Cao Đài temple in Tây Ninh province there is a portion of the temple that is known as the "Càn Khôn" which represents the universe of Ngọc Hoàng Thượng đế (the Jade Emperor, although the term technically means "Pearl Princely Lord-Sovereign" in Vietnamese). Regardless, the point is that this iconography could be understood to be geomorphic. Other forms of common geomorphic iconography include mountains, rivers, clouds, and more. Technically, no other temple is supposed

to have a complete Càn Không, although the decentralization of Cao Đài into a number of different branches (sometimes up to 12 "phái" are counted) has meant that some temples do include representations of the Càn Khôn.

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Yes

Notes: Anthropomorphic iconography mostly comes in terms of the representation of historical figures who have been elevated to the status of saints, gods, immortals, and Buddhas. Sun Yat-Sen, Victor Hugo, Nguyễn Bình Khiêm, Gautama Buddha, Confucius, Jesus of Nazareth, the Prophet Muhammad, Julius Caesar, Pericles, Joan of Arc, Laozi, Fu Xi, and Dipankara Buddha (understood in this context as a historical predecessor to Gautama Buddha). These are just the most notable figures, however. Anthropomorphic iconography is typically divided into four ranks: Thần (gods), Thánh (saints), Tiên (Immortals), and Phật (Buddhas), each of which can be further divided into their association with the heavenly, human, and earthly realms.

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– Yes

Notes: The main supernatural symbol of the Cao Đài, the one true god, is a singular eye in a triangle, in the form of the Eye of Providence or all seeing eye. The symbol was common in Catholic iconography as a representation of the holy trinity, and thus was likely consciously adopted by the Cao Đài in the context of French missionization to non-Christian Vietnamese from the 19th to 20th century. Notably, there are some fifty (50) representations of the "left eye of Cao Đài" (the Cao Đài version of the eye of providence) in the temple in Tây Ninh province.

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: There are several representations of heavenly realms at various locations in Cao Đài temples.

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– Yes

Notes: In addition to the left eye of Cao Đài, Cao Đài religion borrows the Bagua (Eight Trigrams) imagery from Daoism. Further the flag of the Cao Đài represents the Tâm giáo (sanjiao) with yellow for Buddhism, blue for Daoism, and red for Confucianism.

↳ Humans:

– Yes

Notes: Portrayals of humans and anthropomorphic iconography are the same in this case. Anthropomorphic iconography mostly comes in terms of the representation of historical figures who have been elevated to the status of saints, gods, immortals, and Buddhas. All of these individuals are understood to be historical human figures in the Cao Đài understanding of the history of religion on earth. Sun Yat-Sen, Victor Hugo,

Nguyễn Bình Khiêm, Gautama Buddha, Confucius, Jesus of Nazareth, the Prophet Muhammad, Julius Caesar, Pericles, Joan of Arc, Laozi, Fu Xi, and Dipankara Buddha (understood in this context as a historical predecessor to Gautama Buddha). These are just the most notable figures, however. Anthropomorphic iconography is typically divided into four ranks: Thần (gods), Thánh (saints), Tiên (Immortals), and Phật (Buddhas), each of which can be further divided into their association with the heavenly, human, and earthly realms.

↳ Other features of iconography:

– Yes

Notes: Cao Đài iconography is not only incredibly vivid (colorful), it is intentionally complex. The use of coloration in iconography often carries with it additional symbolic meaning, as does the material used to construct the icon (due to associations with five elements, and other additional meanings).

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– No

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– Optional (common)

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: As is common with Vietnamese traditional religion and also the French Catholicism that early Cao Đài adherents would have been exposed to in the context of French Cochinchina-- a distinction between an individual essence or "flame" is understood to be distinct from the physical essences (body). However, whether or not we translate this as a spirit-mind distinction is a matter of translation.

- ↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:
 - Yes

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

- ↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:
 - Yes

- ↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:
 - Yes

- ↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “above” space:
 - Yes

- ↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “below” space:
 - No

- ↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:
 - No

- ↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:
 - Yes [specify]: Cao Đài doctrine specifies that reincarnation in this world is one possible result of the afterlife, as an alternative to ascending in the hierarchy of the spirit world.

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

- ↳ In a human form:
 - Yes

- ↳ In animal/plant form:
 - Yes

- ↳ In form of an inanimate object(s):
 - No

↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage. etc.):

– No

↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma):

– Yes

Notes: Yes, reincarnation is explicitly informed by one's karma. However, reincarnation is not inevitable, it is possible to ascend through the hierarchies of the spirit realm as one alternative to reincarnation.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

↳ Cremation:

– Yes

Notes: Cremation is an acceptable alternative to burial in a cemetery.

↳ Mummification:

– No

– Yes

Notes: There is a single case of mummification of a Cao Đài leader: Phạm Công Tắc (the chief of the Mediums) was mummified upon his death in exile in Cambodia in 1959.

↳ Interment:

– No

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– Yes

↳ Human sacrifices present:

– No

↳ Animal co-sacrifices present:

– No

Notes: If we interpret this question to refer to animals sacrificed on site, the answer is generally no.

– Yes

Notes: If we interpret this question to include any sacrificial food, which may include animals that have been slaughtered, cleaned, and butchered in the past, cooked and prepared, then: yes.

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

↳ Valuable items:

– Yes

↳ Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):

– Yes

Notes: Can be included in burial with a corpse, if personal effects, but likely rare.

↳ Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):

– Yes

Notes: If personal effects, then potentially yes, in a burial, but likely rare.

↳ Other valuable/precious items interred:

– No

↳ Other grave goods:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

Notes: It is possible to have a family have a "family tombstone" in a graveyard, so in this sense, "yes."

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– No

Notes: It is possible to interpret the fact that the "all seeing eye" of the Cao Đài is a "left eye" that this is an anthropomorphic deity. However, believers have not historically understood the essence of the deity itself as anthropomorphic as much as they have understood it as a universal guiding essence.

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– Yes [specify]: Communication, especially through prophets and mediums.

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

Notes: In many interpretations, the supreme high god is unquestionably good, in a fashion that is reminiscent of many Vietnamese and French Catholic interpretations that believers have historically been exposed to in the region.

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: The supreme high god has distinct representations to symbolically take charge of Confucian, Daoist, and Buddhist cosmologies.

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: Cao Đài doctrine indicates that we are presently (20th century onward) in a "third period of redemption" where the unity between God and humans will reach a state that has not yet been imagined.

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can punish:
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
– Yes

Notes: Although possible, this is very rare to see expressed in official writings or opinions from religious elites. Instead, this is more of a "popular sentiment" that might exist among believers who have fallen into hard times.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
– Yes

Notes: Assuming here that "venerate" and "worship" are not the same, it hardly matters, since Cao Đài religion interprets all supernatural beings as ultimate one and the same: a representation of the high god.

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
– Yes [specify]: To demonstrate humility, the Cao Đài high god actually presents itself to humanity as the lowest of rankings of deities and divinities.

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:
– Yes

↳ In dreams:
– Yes

↳ In trance possession:
– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:
– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:
– Yes

Notes: Opinion is divided on this matter. But one possible answer is "yes."

↳ Only through monarch
– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:
– Yes [specify]: Spirit writing

↳ Previously human spirits are present:
– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen:
– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:
– Yes

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:
– Yes

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

Notes: Although often not specified, human spirits have typically not been typically interpreted as omniscient.

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: Although often not specified, human spirits have typically not been typically interpreted as omnipresent.

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– No

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– No

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Notes: If they appear, then yes.

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Notes: If they appear, then yes.

↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Notes: Not all spirits, but those with a direct relation or message to convey to the person who sees them.

↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: This is possible, but seems like a rare message to convey.

↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:

– Yes [specify]: Knowledge of Cao Đài, the community, or how to better serve the community.

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can reward:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can punish:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– No

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination processes:

– Yes

↳ Only through specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Communicate with living through other means:

– Yes [specify]: Spirit writing is a possible form of communication with deceased spirits.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally

visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: They have knowledge specific to their subordinate religious domains.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Yes

Notes: It is possible for some form of non-human supernatural being to possess hunger, specifically ghosts. However, for others it is not common.

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: There is a dualistic relationship between Cao Đài notions of Cao Đài as the heavenly father and the veneration of the "Mother Goddess" of Vietnamese religion as "the mother"

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– Yes

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– Yes [specify]: Divided into their specific affiliation with religious communities (ie.: French, Modern World, Buddhist, Daoist, etc.)

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including

obviously “moral” or “ethical” norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

↳ Food:

– Yes

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: they care about (and oppose) opulent living, caring too much about sensuality

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

Notes: There is an explicit precept against adultery.

↳ Incest:

– Yes

Notes: Opposition to incest is presumed, as this is the norm in all of Vietnamese society and much of Southeast Asia. Most traditional "marriage practices" in the region indicate that a person must "marry out" of their "village" (which is an even broader definition of "extended family" than as written law in the contemporary North Atlantic).

↳ Other sexual practices:

– Yes [specify]: The precept on "adultery" is sometimes interpreted more broadly as "sexual misconduct."

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

Notes: There is an explicit precept that states "do not sin by word," akin to the Buddhist precept of a similar nature. This precept is often interpreted as "do not lie" although it is possible that small little lies to "keep the peace" in a setting where there is a dispute could be considered "not sinning by word" or "lies of omission" could also be considered "not sinning by word." However, the most common interpretation and overarching principle is "do not lie."

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

Notes: The violation of an oath could be considered "sinning by word," as above.

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– No

Notes: There are norms in Vietnamese society that specify hard work as a value, much like there are concepts in religions, such as Christianity, Islam, Confucianism, and Buddhism, which all address laziness. However, the issue is not central to the concerns of the religious group.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

Notes: However, they are pro-sorcery.

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

Notes: A Confucian norm, this is also a norm in Vietnamese society. However, the norm is a mentioned concern in Cao Đài texts. Filial piety and simply "respecting elders" more broadly are serious concerns. In part, they are embedded in the context of the emergence of Cao Đài in conversation with the French enlightenment and colonial modernity.

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Yes

Notes: If gossiping becomes too much, then it becomes "sinning by word."

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

Notes: There is an explicit precept banning stealing, which also implies that broader property crimes would be a concern so long as they fall under the rubric of a form of theft. Destruction of property is not explicitly considered a crime. Destruction of organizational property, however, is, typically.

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Yes

Notes: Most converts to Cao Đài at this stage have entered the community through marriage. However, in the 1930s and 1940s, large numbers of converts joined as a feature of trends of millenarianism that spread across mainland Southeast Asia from the 19th century through the middle of the 20th century.

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

Notes: Implied through the precept of "do not steal,"

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– No

Notes: Although there are hand washing stations at temples, the expectations of maintaining personal hygiene are predominantly implied, rather than explicitly stated.

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: Cao Đài cares about adherence to the "Five Ways": the way of humanity (secular

concerns, a way of social harmony); the way of local spirits (spirits who bless the living if revered properly), the way of the saints (the way of social service, as taught by the world religions); and the way of the immortals (understanding how events unfold natural and emphasizing personal cultivation)

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– No

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: In accordance with karmic principles.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Other forms of karmic judgment apply.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:
– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:
– Yes

↳ Other [specify]
– Yes
Notes: Reunion with ancestors.

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:
– Yes
Notes: This is no longer common, but was particularly common during the decades when Cao Đai groups had their own militias separate from the state.

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:
– Yes
Notes: Although true, Cao Đai community members have become predominantly an urbanized and sub-urban population, meaning the agricultural blessings are not as direct for those members of the Cao Đai community.

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– Yes

Notes: Including diaspora movements from Vietnam, historically.

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Support for an individual entering heaven can be secured via the network of other souls. Gaining the "spiritual support" of other souls is a reward in and of itself for this reason.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– Yes

↳ Alive, identified:

– No

↳ Coming in this lifetime:

– No

↳ Coming on specified date:

– No

↳ Coming in unspecified time in near future:

– No

↳ Coming in unspecified time in distant future:

– Yes

Notes: If one interprets Maitreya Buddha as a messianic figure that appears during the present time of redemption, then yes, this is a future messiah.

↳ Coming has already passed:

– Yes

Notes: Jesus is interpreted as ONE possible messiah, although the meaning of messianism in this context is rather unspecified.

↳ One in a line of many past and future messiahs:

– Yes

Notes: Jesus is interpreted as ONE possible messiah, although the meaning of messianism in this context is rather unspecified. Similarly, a line of Buddhas, from Dipankara through Gautama to Maitreya is identified, but there is not a strong emphasis on the messianic elements of these figures.

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

– No

Notes: Depending on the notion of the messiah, but the most common messiah Cao Đài believers have been familiar with is Jesus. Although there are interpretations that Jesus and the mahdi messiah in Islam do establish political order restoration projects in those traditions, these are not strongly emphasized elements of Cao Đài belief.

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– Yes

↳ Other purpose:

– Yes [specify]: All prophets/messiahs are messengers of God (Cao Đài) and of divine will.

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:

– No

↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton at some other time:

– No

Notes: Because of the varieties of interpretations, there are multiple answers, but the previous timelines (above) cover the possibilities well.

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:

– No

↳ Divine judgment event:

– Yes

↳ Restoration of the world:

– Yes

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:

– Yes

↳ Establishment of a new political system:

– No

↳ Establishment of a new religious system:

– Yes

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:

– Yes

↳ All religious in-group members will survive the eschaton:

– No

↳ A subset of religion in-group members will survive the eschaton:

– Yes

↳ All members of the sample region will survive the eschaton:

– No

↳ Everyone in the world will survive the eschaton:

– No

↳ Other survival condition:

– I don't know

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Strongly present and highlighted

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:

– Yes

↳ Moral norms apply to:

– Only specialized religious class

– Only one class of society

– Only one gender

– All individuals within society (excepting slaves, aliens)

– All individuals within society

– All individuals within contemporary world

– All individuals (any time period)

Notes: Depending on the nature of the moral norm, all of the above. For instance, the five precepts apply to all individuals within Cao Đài communities, but the broader implications of these are understood to apply to all individuals at all times. At the same time, the gendered division of space applies strictly to the Cao Đài ritual context in temples in a way that it does not apply elsewhere. The short answer to this question is: it depends!

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (females):

– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (females):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular

Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Hours: 6

Notes: Prayer times are established as Thời Tý, Thời Mẹo, Thời Ngọ, and Thời Dậu. They are midnight, 6 am, noon, and 6 pm, respectively. There are also rituals on the 1st and 15th day of each lunar month.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Due to the wide variety in size of temples, there is a substantial range for this, but it could be dozens at some temples, ranging to hundreds or even thousands at the main temple.

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Average interval [hours]: 336

Notes: The time between the first and 15th day of a lunar month is 14 days or 336 hours.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Yes

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– Yes

Notes: Fictive kinship terminology is widespread in Vietnam especially, but also more broadly in Southeast Asia, as well.

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Notes: Cao Đài religion developed to the extent that one branch of the religion established their own paramilitary contingent large enough to be considered "the Cao Đài army." It took the threat of military violence and serious diplomatic negotiations to get the Cao Đài army to submit to subordination by the Republic of Vietnam.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Notes: This was especially true in the context of food shortages resulting from the Second Indochina War.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Although variable at times, by the post colonial period, both the Democratic Republic of Vietnam and the Republic of Vietnam had established institutions for famine relief, in part a concern brought to the fore by the 1945 famine in northern Vietnam.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1954 CE - 2024 CE

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Vietnam

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Although not as successful as intended, the Socialist Republic of Vietnam has provided poverty relief since 1976. The government approved a new measure of a multi-dimensional poverty line in 2021, meaning the government now not only measures extreme poverty but also measures vulnerability to poverty. The expanded definitions of "poverty" have ensured that an additional 10 million people - or more than one tenth of the national population - will qualify for government support between 2021 and 2025.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1976 CE - 2024 CE

Region: Vietnam

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Yes

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: However, most elder care in Vietnam is still provided by the family.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1976 CE - 2024 CE

Region: Vietnam

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: However, this is only for religious training.

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Yes

Notes: However, these only apply to the grounds of Cao Đài temple complexes. In most cases, the temple grounds are too small for this to be substantial. However, at the main temple complex in Tây Ninh, they are substantial.

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– Yes

Notes: Trình Minh Thế led the Cao Đài militia until 1955. The militia operated as an institutionalized police force. On February 13, 1955, the troops were integrated into the Army of the Republic of Vietnam, ending this era.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1945 CE - 1955 CE

Region: Vietnam

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Notes: However, the group does employ the terminology of both a "legislative" and "judiciary" element to their social organization. At the same time, a close examination of Cao Đài history suggests the "judiciary" is predominantly active in the metaphorical and metaphysical sense.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Yes

Notes: All answers are relative to Trình Minh Thế's militia.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1945 CE - 1955 CE

Region: Vietnam

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1945 CE - 1955 CE

Region: Vietnam

Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1945 CE - 1955 CE

Region: Vietnam

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1945 CE - 1955 CE

Region: Vietnam

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1945 CE - 1955 CE

Region: Vietnam

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1945 CE - 1955 CE

Region: Vietnam

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– Yes

Notes: All answers for these questions apply to Trình Minh Thế's paramilitary group that grew into a de facto army and was later incorporated into the Army of the Republic of Vietnam.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1945 CE - 1955 CE

Region: Vietnam

Does the religious group in question have the power to conscript:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1945 CE - 1955 CE

Region: Vietnam

Does the religious group in question maintain a full-time military corps (e.g. Swiss Guard):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1945 CE - 1955 CE

Region: Vietnam

Does the religious group in question maintain a standing army:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1945 CE - 1955 CE

Region: Vietnam

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– Yes

Is use of this distinct written language confined to religious professionals:

– Yes

Notes: In the sense that there is an understanding that the esoteric Vietnamese language may be confined to the knowledge of the realm of religious elites. No one else is expected to understand this form of (very complex) Sino-Vietnamese language.

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Standard Vietnamese in both Quốc ngữ (modern) and Chữ Nôm (traditional character) writing systems.

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Vietnamese in quốc ngữ is considered the language of the state in Vietnam. Although there is no official language in the United States, the majority of languages in the communities where Cao Đài adherents live in the United States are English and Spanish.

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Gathering
- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Fishing
- Pastoralism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Notes: All of these are normal food production activities in the Greater Mekong Delta region. In the diaspora, the primary method of gathering food is probably "shopping" although some small-scale horticulture is commonly practiced in the diaspora as well.

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Gathering
- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Fishing
- Patorialism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Notes: Commercial food production has also become increasingly available from the earliest days of the Cao Đài religion through the present.

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